

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

A novel buffering fault-tolerance approach for network on chip (NoC)

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Abstract

Network-on-Chip (NoC) is a key component in chip multiprocessors (CMPs) as it supports communication between many cores. NoC is a network-based communication subsystem on an integrated circuit, most typically between modules in a system on a chip (SoC). Designing a reliable NoC against failures that can prevent failure using some measures or preventing error or system failure while failure happens and proper performance became a significant concern. For a reliable design against failures, first, the system should be analysed to discover the critical points. Hence, in this research, it is tried first to investigate the scale of fault tolerance effect on the mechanism in the router on the network by injecting simulated errors, and then these errors are prevented. As the major novelty, the authors implemented a router on a synchronised network and calculated the network buffering fault tolerance by injecting error in the buffer. Specifically, a new method for improving fault tolerance is proposed, which uses the existing resources efficiently. So, it does not impose any overhead on hardware and improves the error tolerance scale. The authors also evaluate it from different perspectives to show its superior performance.

KEYWORDS

buffering, error injection, network on chip (NoC), router, virtual channel

1 | INTRODUCTION

Network-on-chip (NoC) refers to closed-switch communication in a large VLSI system implemented on a single silicon chip. This concept was introduced to improve the bandwidth of the electrical connections of recent system-on-chips (SoCs). The superiority of NoC interconnects mitigates the

challenges of growing to interconnect complexity and power budget requirements, making it significant for scalable architectures. Fault-tolerant routing algorithms are primarily designed to fortify the network against permanent errors. The first valuable designs for NoCs are introduced in Ref. [1–3]. In most previous studies, the routing algorithms are designed for situations when one or more areas of the network face

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problems due to a permanent error. In these algorithms, failure of the nodes that contain router and processing sources is the primary concern, and it is assumed that any permanent error in a node leads to the loss of that node. The first helpful research about fault-tolerant connections on NoC was proposed in 2003 to deliver the package to its destination when a permanent or transient error happens by using a series of random connections similar to random gossip protocols [4]. The main problem with this method is that it is only useful for low traffic, and when the traffic volume is medium or high, this method causes more traffic. In Ref. [5], which is in pursuit of Ref. [4], a technique for tolerating a series of permanent and transient faults with a flooding algorithm and random walk is proposed.

Other research studies about fault-tolerant routers is proposed in Ref. [6–9]. In Ref. [6], distance vector routing and link status algorithms tolerate permanent errors in routers and links. In Ref. [7], network reliability against permanent errors in links is improved by reconfiguring and adding automatic re-routing features to switches. Also, in Ref. [8], a routing algorithm based on source routing is proposed, which is more efficient compared to previous algorithms. This algorithm consists of two parts, discovering and maintaining the route. With this approach, nodes discover all the routes between the source and destinations in NoC. In the meantime, using them, they will maintain the routes. In Ref. [9], a structure for the NoC router and its routing algorithm to encounter the permanent errors in links is proposed, which like Ref. [10], consists of two sections. In the first section, the network is searched to find a route between each pair of sources and destinations. This action occurs on each new start or reconfiguration of the system after each troubleshooting. In the second part, the found and saved routes are used for data connection in the normal status of the system. In Ref. [11], a comparative routing algorithm for tolerating the permanent faults in switches and links is proposed. The traffic is distributed evenly on the network and prevents congestion around a link or a switch. This research uses the same effect of a switch or link in a congested network around the switch or on a link.

The design features of NoC components affect the key performance criteria of the communication context, such as latency and throughput. While bandwidth is widely available in NoCs, many efforts are made to reduce network latency, which may violate the performance specifications of applications. Under heavy traffic conditions, the rapid spread of packets across the network and the low unemployment of network resources are key requirements for efficient communication architectures. Flow control determines how network resources are allocated to packets passing through the network and can be considered a resource allocation problem or dispute resolution.

In some of the proposed NoC architectures, flow control is combined with error control in an integrated mechanism. Error control is becoming a growing concern due to the increasing impact on signal reliability, such as interference, power supply noise, EMI, and soft errors. Malfunctions can be detected in the hardware using error correction or error detection/retransmission mechanisms or at higher network layers (for example,

the connection-oriented transmission layer). However, fast error recovery requires the implementation of error control hardware, thus increasing the complexity of the switch and/or NI. Reusing flow control mechanisms for error management saves some space and power and prevents duplication of control lines.

This work focusses on implicit exchanges in providing different levels of fault tolerance support in buffer architectures. We consider different mechanisms for allocating buffer and channel bandwidth in NoC pipe architecture [6]. Different flow control techniques for different buffer locations and management strategies are considered and adapted to work with pipeline links, where data entry rates can be separated by link length.

2 | BACKGROUND AND FAULT-TOLERANT ROUTING ALGORITHM DESIGN

The simplest flow control mechanisms are without buffer. Memory-free switches are used in Ref. [9]: when congested, packets propagate in a non-ideal direction, also known as deflection routing. Unauthorised loop containers and temporary networks introduced guaranteed bandwidth in Ref. [12]. Providing QoS by creating circuits between communication nodes requires some buffer resources. A new packet-based tuning hybrid circuit switching has been reported in Ref. [8], which requires minimal buffer resources, capable of holding only one request packet. The NoC switch circuit is reported using time-division multiplexing in Ref. [13, 14].

A chain of cause and effect that extends across several layers must be considered in fault tolerance research. At the bottom layer, physical failure mechanisms cause primary devices such as transistors or wires to fail. In the next higher layer, such a failure is modelled as an error. The set of all modelled errors constitutes the error model. This includes the impact of errors, fault locations, and more potential parameters such as duration and probability of error. The most straightforward and extensive digital circuit error model shows the output of logic gates in specific values.

To evaluate the fault-tolerant networks on the chip, we organise the layers based on the OSI reference model of communication protocols (Figure 1). In particular, the data link layer, the network layer, and the transmission layer are considered in this study [15]. Higher layers related to application software and middleware are not considered here because they assume that the data transfer layer is transmitting. The physical layer is related to the transfer of information units (phit), which is not explicitly considered in this survey because it involves a large amount of research work and is not specific to NoCs.

In the data link layer, reliable data transfer and flow control are implemented. The network layer is responsible for switching and routing. Finally, the NoC transfer layer provides transfer across data packets. A pack consists of one or more flutes that are moved one after the other, and a flit may consist of several fits.

Fault-tolerant routing algorithms are mostly designed to fortify the network against permanent errors. The first useful

FIGURE 1 Network on Chip layers and modules

designs for NoCs are introduced in Ref. [13]. In most previous studies, the routing algorithms are designed for situations when one or more areas of the network face problems due to a permanent error. In these algorithms, failure of the nodes that contain router and processing sources is the main concern, and it is assumed that any permanent error in a node leads to the loss of that node. The first useful research about fault-tolerant connections on NoC was proposed in 2003 to deliver the package to its destination when a permanent or transient error happens by using a series of random connections similar to random gossip protocols [16]. The main problem with this method is that it is only useful for low traffic, and when the traffic volume is medium or high, this method causes more traffic. In Ref. [17], which is in pursuit of Ref. [16], a method for tolerating a series of permanent and transient faults with flooding algorithms and random walk is proposed.

Following that, other research studies about fault-tolerant routers are proposed in Ref. [12, 17–21]. In Ref. [17], by distance vector routing and link status algorithms, permanent errors that happen in routers and links are tolerated. In Ref. [18], network reliability against permanent errors in links is improved with reconfiguring and adding automatic re-routing features to switches. Also, in Ref. [12], a routing algorithm based on source routing is proposed, which is more efficient

compared to previous algorithms. This algorithm consists of two parts, discovering and maintaining the route. With this approach, nodes discover all the routes between the source and destinations in NoC; in the meantime, using them, they will maintain the routes. In Ref. [19], a structure for NoC router and its routing algorithm to encounter the permanent errors in links is proposed, which like Ref. [20] consists of two sections. In the first section, the network is searched to find a route between each pair of sources and destination. This action occurs on each new start or reconfiguration of the system after each troubleshooting. In the second part, the found and saved routes are used in for data connection in the normal status of the system. In Ref. [21], a comparative routing algorithm for tolerating the permanent faults in switches and links is proposed in which the traffic is distributed evenly on the network and prevents congestion around a link or a switch. This research uses the same effect of a switch or link in a congested network around the switch or on a link.

Although the current literature includes previous efforts in various fields in NoC, this study differs considerably in scope, focusses on the latest developments, and has the primary goal of evaluating energy efficiency in different techniques and designs. For example, the authors in Ref. [16] discussed NoC programming models and provided only a tabular analysis of

topologies and switching techniques. However, this study did not focus on energy efficiency.

Routing algorithms for NoCs are discussed in Ref. [15, 17, 22–29], but this study did not consider energy efficiency. However, it did not consider the study of power consumption in NoC. The authors in Ref. [18] sufficiently discuss the existing approaches to NoC and analyse the networks in terms of probabilistic and deterministic design approaches, along with designs inspired by statistical physics. Our paper fully covers many of the recent research efforts that have affected SoC/NoC energy efficiency in each of our areas of focus. In addition, we believe that this study will be helpful to researchers in finding the latest research on energy-efficient designs and techniques for NoC in one place.

3 | FAULT INJECTION BY SOFTWARE

In this method, the injection is done by a series of software in the physical system. Flexibility and cheapness compared to physical injection are some of its features. However, it is probable that the effects of error occurrence in the real world could not be completely simulated in this method. This is due to the low access rate of access features and also the lack of information about the software used for simulation. There are two ways to implement this technique. One of these techniques is pre-runtime fault injection. In this method, we inject the faults into the system before the programme related to a calculating system is used. One of the benefits of this method is its speed since the programme does not need to stop when it is running or being delayed using interrupts. The other method is called run-time fault injection. In this approach, besides using the software to inject the faults, another software is needed for initialisation, and also, the conversions related to fault injections have been used in run time. Interrupts and breaking points are used in this method to move from the main programme to the injection programme.

3.1 | Fault injection process

As was mentioned before, based on the features of the simulated fault injection method, which are useable in the initial phases of design, we also used these methods in this thesis to calculate the level of reliability in NoC router [30–34]. The usage of simulated fault injection is considered in many types of research related to the reliability assessment of digital calculating systems. Providing different tools for this purpose by other research groups in various universities is another acceptable reason for using this method. In this thesis, the SI injection tool is used to study the level of NoC router tolerance.

Figure 2 shows an overview of these main tools and interactions for setting up and performing error injection tests. The injection medium for error injection studies consists of three main independent phases. Startup phase, simulation phase, and evaluation phase.

The primary purpose of this injection medium is to investigate the SEU and MBU error propagation analysis and

FIGURE 2 The injection environment

to extract parameters such as published error percentage, hidden error percentage, and error propagation delay [35]. This tool can inject fault in simulated environments by VHDL and Verilog hardware description languages. It should be noted that these tools countered minor problems with VHDL hardware description language, which can be easily encountered by familiarity with VHDL language [22–24, 30, 36].

3.2 | SI performance

This tool operates the injection process with the help of a series of fault injection units (FIU) in the destination system, in which its tolerance level is measured. Each of these FIUs is triggered by fault injection signals (FIS). As it is mentioned in 1.4, the importance of these transient faults is way more than the permanent faults. A lot of recent reports and research also discussed transient faults. On the other hand, since the probability of a fault occurring is low, the chance of multiple faults occurring is very low that it is close to 0, and in some systems, their occurrence is known to be not possible (however, this probability can change due to the environment which the system is working in). Based on what is said, the SI fault injection tool has the ability to implement the simulation of transient or permanent faults with defining periods of time for FISs [37, 38].

On the other hand, this simulator activates one of FISs in each iteration of the test to check the effects of a single fault. In fact, the SI fault injection tool consists of three independent phases to study the reliability of a simulated system with VHDL and Verilog languages. These phases are shown in Figure 3, which are the fault injection phase, simulation phase, and evaluation phase.

In the injection phase, different types of fault, their places, their active time, and test repetition number are

defined. Studying each section in a system and recognising their circuits before injecting any fault can lead to acceptable results. In the simulation phase, with the help of the Modelsim simulator, we repeat the simulation for activation of each FIS defined in phase one. The SI tool has the ability to determine the range of activation for FISs in each iteration with an exponential distribution which the average of it was asked from the user in the first phase. Therefore, in each simulation iteration, which activates a specific FIS, different periods of time are considered for FISs. Also, the activation time in the authorised period for fault injection is determined with uniform distribution [23, 34, 36]. Increasing the number of iterations makes the results closer to the acceptable result, which is also time-consuming. It is a barrier to doing the test with lots of iterations. SI tool saves

the results of repeated tests on a list of signals (which includes middle signals and signals which are the result) and names it as 16 faulty execution [39].

Running the test without activating any of the FISs is 17 faultless execution (or 18 golden execution), which gives another list of evaluating signals to the user, which are the results of the simulation running normally. Another important notation in this phase that should be noted is the authorised periods we define for activation of FISs. To achieve precise and reliable results, the start of this period should be in a range where the system is in a steady state. Also, the end of this period of time should be at a suitable interval from the main programme end time. Considering this will help injected FISs to have enough time to affect the system and be seen in the results [40].

FIGURE 3 Overview of software fault injection (SINJECT)

TABLE 1 Injected fault comparison based on failure rate and propagated faults

Input buffer	Total	Real fault injections	Failed experiments	Fault propagation rate	Failure rate
Cross talk	900	534	188	59	35
Dead clause	600	237	193	39	81
Micro-operation	500	266	249	53	93
Stuck then	300	83	46	27	54
SEU	1800	819	244	45	29
Total	4100	1939	920	47	47

TABLE 2 Injected fault comparison

Virtual channel 2	Total	Real fault injections	Failed experiments	Fault propagation rate	Failure rate
Cross talk	1200	732	293	61	40
Dead clause	400	80	51	20	64
Micro-operation	1400	672	564	48	84
SEU	2200	1188	297	54	25
Stuck then	300	93	49	31	53
Total	5500	2765	1254	50	45

TABLE 3 Injected fault comparison

Virtual channel 4	Total	Real fault injections	Failed experiments	Fault propagation rate	Failure rate
Cross talk	1400	938	394	67	42
Dead clause	400	84	54	21	64
Micro-operation	1400	658	566	47	86
SEU	2400	1176	259	49	22
Stuck then	300	93	50	31	54
Total	5900	2949	1323	49	44

TABLE 4 Injected fault comparison

Output buffer	Total	Real fault injections	Failed experiments	Fault propagation rate	Failure rate
Cross talk	1800	1404	632	78	45
Dead clause	300	48	30	16	62
Micro-operation	800	344	268	43	78
SEU	3300	2211	840	67	38
Stuck then	300	60	30	20	50
Total	6500	4067	1800	62	44

TABLE 5 Fault injection results

Module	Real fault injection	Failed experiments	Average of fault latency	Fault propagation rate	Recovered	Latent
Input buffer	1939	920	241	47	47	52
Output buffer	4067	1800	174	62	44	56
Virtual channel 2	2765	1254	234	50	45	54
Virtual channel 4	2949	1323	250	49	44	56

4 | EXPERIMENT RESULTS

As it was mentioned in previous sections, the basis of evaluation in fault injection experiments is the number of faults (real ones) propagated in the system. With an understanding of this, the designer of SI tool made it possible to identify these faults in the system, and other calculations can be done based on them. Tables 1–4 shows the amount of propagated faults, replaced faults with new values, hidden faults inside the system, failure rate, and faults propagation delay in each type of router buffering model on the network separately and based on percentage and amount.

One of the measures to evaluate the precision and correctness of the injection method is to calculate the amount of propagated faults in the target system, in other words, the rate of them to all of the injected faults. In an easier way, the bigger the value, the more sections of the system were tested. In values shown in Table 1–5, an acceptable percentage of injected faults propagated in the system shows the coverage rate of faults in the router buffer on the network and the precision of the experiment on it.

Since the reported amount of hidden fault rate is low, ranking different buffers is based on new values replacement

with the fault effect, which is labelled as Recovered in the table, which is the opposite of failure rate ranking. To justify this, it should be noted that the buffering unit actively sends and receives each flit and reads the new inputs. Therefore, new data for replacement enter it with higher frequency, and the high rate reported for new data replacement with fault effects is higher. While a low percentage of hidden faults is not desirable since it shows that many of the faults will cause failure after turning into errors, it also indicates that the system does not have the potential to turn a lot of errors into failure simultaneously.

5 | CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

With the growth of technology and the daily scaling of transistors, the complexity of the multi-processors on-chip is increasing. Increasing the number of existing processing resources in the chip design requires the usage of a suitable communication platform for connections between them. Overall, the communication structures on chips should have certain properties such as high performance, being structured, reusability, and scalability. System on chips (SoC) is proposed

as a solution to this problem by using the bus structure as the implementation technique. The bus structure used in SoCs does not have scalability and has some restrictions in the reusability aspect. Therefore, a new concept, the title of a network on chip (NoC) is proposed as a solution to this problem.

Advances in NOC technology have consequences such as reducing circuit capacitors' capacity and voltage levels of the power supply and logic. These consequences have increased the sensitivity of the gates, flip-flops, and memory units used to ambient noise and charged particles, leading to errors and eventual breakdowns. For this reason, designing fault-tolerant systems that can prevent the production of false results or destructive effects is of particular importance. In this paper, we have designed a buffer fault-tolerant router with an efficient level and power consumption. In this method, we have used free or idle virtual channels to store plugin packages. The virtual channel has been implemented as two channels in order to avoid deadlock. The proposed structure was implemented in VHDL and examined with the CAD tool, and it was shown that the proposed method occupies less space, has less power consumption, and also has a shorter critical path. As mentioned, increasing the number of transistors in the chip, reducing power consumption, and reducing the level of logic sensitivity are inevitable. It seems that fault-tolerant methods are more popular than in the past, and therefore it is very appropriate to continue research and investigation in this field. It is suggested that in order to increase and improve the tolerability in the chip network, research be done in the areas of design of routing algorithms and structure of routers.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest associated in this manuscript.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analysed in this study.

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